

ENVRI-FAIR WP5 TF1 Catalogue

Task Force - overview

Daniele Bailo and TF1 task force

1. Objectives

The main objective of this Task Force is to agree and implement a metadata catalogue schema and associated management services, with the aim of describing and providing access to assets available from the ENVRI RIs. This can be potentially used as ENVRI- EOSC catalogue, after appropriate transformation to match EOSC requirements..

2. Approach

2.1 Heterogeneity of Research Infrastructures

Existing research infrastructures in the framework of ENVRI-FAIR are part of a common landscape but with consistent differences in terms of:

- (i) presenting and accessing datasets, which span from machine-readable solutions (e.g. services with RESTful webapis) to human-accessible only portals;
- (ii) datasets (and other assets) and some description of their actual contents:
 - formats, spanning from binary files, to .csv and proprietary formats, or in some cases well defined standards (e.g. NetCDF);
 - as well as the semantics (formal descriptions of the fields therein) that are key to the interoperability
- (iii) way of accessing datasets and other assets e.g. services and consequent metadata description, spanning from location based search to parameter-based selections and/or 'keyword' terms or free-text terms;
- (iv) resources of interests, spanning from services, datasets, to source codes or documents
- (v) audiences served, spanning from individual researchers, collaborations and RIs, to automated harvesters and linked virtual research environments

In such a complex landscape, the common goal is to achieve interoperability through semantic and technical harmonisation driven by FAIR principles.

2.2 Achieving Interoperability

Interoperability can be obtained by following FAIR principles and adopting appropriate technologies to implement them. In particular, a rich metadata schema is necessary to accommodate the existing complexity. This schema must also be able to facilitate representing information related to resources (services, datasets, codes etc), publications, persons, organisations, facilities, equipment, authorisation details and others, in a machine-readable and machine-understandable way.

2.3 Rich Metadata Catalogue

Simply combining the metadata from the RIs is not enough, because they need to be harmonised. This is the function of a canonical superset-rich metadata catalogue that can represent descriptions of services from RIs implementing rich metadata. This will ensure actual machine readability and machine understandability, together with formal syntax and declared semantics.

Processes to fill the homogeneous catalogue with heterogeneous individual information by RIs is also required. The catalogue will be filled with existing resources and assets, which will be represented by metadata records describing, datasets, services, workflows/tools, e-services and other assets such as equipment.

2.4 EOSC Interoperability

In this framework, interoperability with the EOSC catalogue is intended as a two-way process: from the ENVRI-FAIR catalogue of services to the EOSC catalogue (ENVRI-to-EOSC), and vice versa (EOSC-to-ENVRI). The ENVRI-to-EOSC process will guarantee that **ENVRI is the entry point for providing details about ENV RIs, that can be in turn harvested by the EOSC catalogue.**

The EOSC-to-ENVRI process guarantees that users searching the EOSC catalogue will invoke services from ENV RIs, and that the EOSC catalogue can be used by ENVRI for making usage of EOSC resources.

Both processes require technical procedures for mapping metadata, and this is to be discussed within this task force

2.5 Governance

Responsible Research and Innovation (RRI) includes ethics, gender balance, governance, open access, public engagement, and science and education. This should inform the processes around the metadata catalogue, which in turn define what information is required in the catalogue to fulfil those processes. Security and privacy are key aspects within governance.

3. Current work

3.1 Landscaping exercise

Before proposing fit-for-purpose technical solutions, we are undergoing a landscaping exercise which will report on the status of all RIs within the TF1, concentrating on the methodologies used to access their resources (datasets, software codes etc.).

3.2 Capturing RIs heterogeneity

The above exercise, still ongoing but progressing well, is showing that many infrastructures provide access to their assets by means of services, others use only GUIs for human interactions, and mixed scenarios are also present (e.g. computational through web-APIs). This heterogeneity will be captured in a common canonical superset-rich metadata description.

3.3 Convergence on the definition of “services”

The ongoing discussion is also showing the need for a common jargon, especially concerning key words such as “services”, which are interpreted differently according to the background. In this context we propose “services” to be used not only with (a) its pure technical meaning, that is to say RESTful or SOAP services that provide access in a programmatic way to resources, but also (b) in a looser way, everything that implements a functionality that serves for a purpose (e.g. a map-GUI to browse a dataset).

3.4 Convergence on metadata required for the catalogue

Initial discussions pointed out the inadequacy of the metadata schema proposed in the context of EOSC Hub, inherited from eInfracentral, as it is tailored for describing computational-like eInfrastructures rather than RIs that provide data. ENVRIplus concluded with trials of two homogenising metadata schemes, namely CKAN, as used by EUDAT, and CERIF, as used by EPOS. ENV RIs were invited to try these solutions and conclude what they wanted for any common catalogue. In this sense, an existing, well-tested option is on the table, that is to say the CERIF metadata catalogue already used by the EPOS RIs.

4. Conclusion

TF1 has made good progress. We now face much work to characterise the metadata catalogues of the RIs, discover commonalities and differences and move towards a common catalogue schema.

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